

The future of Blockchain Technology

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Over the years, technology has come a long way. And virtual reality (VR) is the proof of it. This particular technology has been gaining rapid popularity and even now, its broad range of benefits remain to be implemented. Another great technology is the blockchain that is ensuring better security for transparent transactions and information shared across the globe.

2. Vision

Ultimately, Project Districts will be a thoroughly robust ecosystem where productivity, recreation, and innovation come to roost, much similar to the real world, only this time without its associated complexities. Our goal is to be the world's first ubiquitous interface for propagating traditional and ethereal experiences to both the everyday internet user and the tech-savvy geek.

2018 will be even bigger for companies to utilize this new form of capital raising.

3. Problem

In today's world, imagination is fettered by uncertainties and innovation remains bound by 21st-century limitations – but how about a world where you're free to do as you please. Free to innovate, free to create, free to interact and integrate – that world is Districts.

4. Solution

To create this world, the Districts development team recruited the services of two innovative technologies, the blockchain, and Virtual Reality - each disruptive in its own right. Project Districts leverages the core efficiencies of these two, to create an immersive virtual ecosystem, complete with virtualized real-life entities existing in a real-time interactive environment.

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5. Features

The main features of the Districts world are; 3DCoin Blockchain, Decentralized Hosting, Decentralized Applications, Districts Visual Studio (DVS), Land Tokens, 3DCoin Mining, Coin Blend, Sub Currencies, Conditional Transactions.

6. Keywords

Project Districts; Virtual Reality; Blockchain Technology; 3D DAPPS; 3DCoin; Districts Visual Studio (DVS), Mining; Conditional Transactions

Author biography

Rezig Zain Laabidine An autodidactic developer from his earliest age, he started a self-employed freelancer programmer in 2010, and contract software developer, for three years. Than he started his company “Blockchain Technology LLC” in Dubai.

During this time, he researched and followed decentralized system and thoroughly followed the crypto currency evolution starting from Bitcoin step by step, mastering all its aspects.

By believing in the future of cryptocurrency and driven by his Gaming and 3D modeling passion, the Project Districts was born.